

**EDUCATIONAL IDEAS IN ANCIENT EASTERN CIVILIZATIONS
(BABYLON, EGYPT, CHINA, INDIA)**

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Abstract. *This article presents information about the ancient Eastern civilizations and their societies that for the first time in human history formed centralized states, writing, law, education, and social institutions. Based on sources, it is shown that these regions - Babylon (Mesopotamia), Egypt, China, and India - occupied an important place in history not only for the achievements of material culture, but also for their educational systems and ideas.*

Keywords: *East, civilization, humanity, centralized states, writing, law, educational and social institutions, formed societies, regions - Babylon (Mesopotamia), Egypt, China and India, material culture, achievements, educational system and ideas, education, ancient times, personality formation, social system, transmission of knowledge from generation to generation, main ideas and methods.*

Ancient Eastern civilizations are the first societies in human history to form centralized states, writing, law, education, and social institutions. These regions—Babylon (Mesopotamia), Egypt, China, and India—play an important role in history not only for their material cultural achievements, but also for their educational systems and ideas. Education has been a means of shaping personality, strengthening social order, and transmitting knowledge from generation to generation since ancient times. This article analyzes the educational systems, their main ideas, and methods in ancient Eastern civilizations.[1;14]

Educational ideas were widely developed in ancient Babylonia (Mesopotamia).

Mesopotamia — an ancient civilization located in what is now Iraq — is known as the land where the first writing system (cuneiform) was invented. During the Babylonian period, education was mainly shaped to meet religious and practical needs. Cuneiform schools of writing and legal education were called “edubba.” In these schools, students learned the basics of writing, mathematics, law, geography, and theology. The laws of Hammurabi were widely disseminated through education.

In terms of social stratification, education was mainly intended for the children of nobles and temple servants. Students were given practical skills such as accounting, tax systems, and drawing up commercial documents. The Babylonian education system was centralized, strictly regulated, and had a religious and legal content. In ancient Egypt, however, the ideas of education differed from the above. In ancient Egypt, education was mainly controlled by state agencies and temples. The goal of education in this system was to educate citizens who were loyal to the state, morally mature, and knowledgeable. Since the Pharaoh was considered a divine figure as a divine basis, education also had a religious character. The basics of theology, astronomy, and art were taught.[2; 40]

The teaching of hieroglyphic writing was central. The “School of Scribes” directed to elite professions.

As a practical education, school graduates worked in administrative, engineering, tax collection, and land surveying. Discipline, obedience, and moral purity were the main values in Egyptian education.

In ancient China, educational ideas were distinguished by their order and style. Education in China developed on the basis of Confucian teachings. He put forward the idea of managing society on the basis of humanity, social duty, respect, and order. Confucianism was at the heart of the Chinese education system, aiming to develop morality, spirituality, respect for parents, and preparation for public service. The state examination system, on the other hand, began in the 3rd century BC, when a test system was introduced for entering the civil service. This developed the idea of meritocracy.

Of the subjects, great attention was paid to history, philosophy, mathematics, literature and music. The Chinese education system has long played a key role in maintaining stability in society and providing educated personnel.

Educational ideas were of particular importance in ancient India. The Vedas, Upanishads and Buddhist teachings were of great importance in the development of education in India. The Vedic education system taught the children of the Brahmin class Vedic knowledge - religious rituals, Sanskrit language, philosophy, astronomy. Education was carried out in gurukuls (teacher's houses). In terms of moral education, personal education was established based on the ideas of Ahimsa (abstinence from violence), satya (truthfulness), karma and dharma.[3; 245]

Universities The first universities such as Takshala and Nalanda appeared in India. Philosophy, medicine, mathematics, grammar and art were taught in these places. Indian education was distinguished by its spiritual, moral, and philosophical depth.

In ancient Eastern civilizations, educational systems were formed in accordance with social, religious and political needs. Their common features are as follows:

- Education was mainly based on religious and moral ideas.
- It was intended for the elite class and served as a means of strengthening social stratification.
- Writing, mathematics, law and moral education played an important role.
- In China, the idea of meritocracy was strong, and in India, a spiritual and philosophical approach was strong.

Traces of the ancient Eastern educational system, particularly the ideas of moral education, interdisciplinary approach, and service to the community, are clearly visible in today's modern education systems. Therefore, this ancient experience serves as an important source for modern pedagogical ideas and practices.

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